

**OPTIMIZATION OF PROCESS PARAMETERS FOR FUSED
FILAMENT FABRICATION USING TOOL PATH REVERSING**Vishal Hayagrivan^{1,2} and Vasan C. S. Chandrasekaran²¹KTH Royal institute of technology, Teknikringen 8, 114 28 Stockholm,

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²RISE SICOMP AB, Argongatan 30, 431 53 Mölndal, vasan.churchill@ri.sewebsite: <https://www.swerea.se/sicomp>**Keywords:** Additive manufacturing, fused filament fabrication, fused deposition modelling, Process parameters, Optimization, Tool path reversing, GCode parser, Stiffness prediction**ABSTRACT**

Fused filament fabrication (FFF) is one of the most economical additive manufacturing techniques. The difficulty in estimating the effects of process parameters on the mechanical properties of the manufactured part, hinders the wide spread industrial adaptation of FFF.

The quality of a part manufactured by FFF highly depends on the process parameters so, it is imperative to develop a technique to fine tune the process parameters. The large number of process parameters and complex relationship between the geometry, parameters and mechanical properties makes it impractical to derive an analytical or an empirical relationship and calls for the use of a finite element (FE) model. A few commercially available FE packages support the simulation of a select types of additive manufacturing techniques – such packages primarily focus on metal additive manufacturing.

A novel method to automatically build a FE model from a geometry and given process parameters is developed in this paper. Image recognition techniques are used to analyse the GCode instructions to build a FE model. As the FE model is built by using the same instruction set a FFF machine uses to manufacture the part, the generated FE model will encompass the effects of all parameters which affect the mechanical behaviour of the manufactured part. The automatic generation of a FE model enables the optimization of the FFF parameters.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fused filament fabrication (and additive manufacturing (AM) in general) gives better design freedom compared to conventional subtractive manufacturing techniques. The design freedom stems from the layer-by-layer manufacturing technique employed by FFF. The sequential deposition of material makes it possible to manufacture complex geometries with relative ease. The design freedom facilitated by FFF comes at the cost of having to define numerous process parameters. The quality and mechanical properties of a manufactured part depends on the process parameters. Lack of tools and models to describe the effects of the process parameters on the properties of the manufactured part restricts the industrial popularity of FFF [1, 2].

The process parameters governing FFF are highly interdependent and must be tailored for the geometry, material properties and in some cases, environmental conditions [7]. An analytical model describing these relationships does not exist and numerical models are very limited. Experimental studies have been conducted in an attempt to describe these relationships. A large number of FFF parameters demands the manufacture of a large number of samples. Empirical models also tend to be geometry specific so, empirical models are not practical and cannot be generalized.

Manufacturing a component with FFF will create process related geometric artefacts and patterns. These artefacts and patterns are not captured in the original CAD model of the part and they have a great influence on the mechanical properties of the manufactured part. An FE analysis based on the original CAD model will be an approximation of the mechanical behaviour of the manufactured part.

Ashu Garg et al. [3] and Miquel Dominogo-Espi et al. [4] have manually created CAD models of the manufactured part comprising the FFF processes related artefacts and patterns. The CAD models were meshed and analysed with an FE package. Such models are tedious to create and cannot be parametrized because FFF parameters have a complex effect on the geometry. Attempting an optimization on such a model is impractical.

Nektarios Georgios Tsoutsos et al. [5] proposed a method to generate a 3D CAD model by analysing instructions sent to the FFF machine (GCode). Such a CAD model will contain the artefacts and patterns generated by the FFF manufacturing technique. The method developed in this paper shares the fundamental idea with N. G. Tsoutsos et al's method but differs in the implementation.

1.1 FFF PARAMETERS

Layer height

The layer-by-layer manufacturing technique requires the input geometry to be sliced into layers before further processing. The thickness of the slices is defined by the layer height parameter. Layer height is illustrated in figure 1(a).

Extrusion width

Defines the width of the extrudate. The cross section of an extruded section can be approximated to a rectangle with circular ends (fig. 1(a)).

Perimeters

Governs the number of roads extruded at the free edges. 2 perimeters are extruded in figure 1(b).

Infill type

Defines the tool path pattern on the inside the perimeters of a layer (fig. 1(b)). In figure 1 (b), a honeycomb pattern can be observed.

Infill density

Defines the amount of material in each layer. In figure 1(b), the honeycomb pattern is filled at 40% density.

Infill angle

Defines the orientation of the infill. In figure 1(b), the honeycomb structure is oriented at an angle of 45°.

FIGURE 1. (a) Layer height and extrusion width (b) Perimeters and fill pattern

2 SIMULATION METHOD

Information like the extruder movements, amount of material extruded is interpreted from the GCode and is used to digitally recreate the FFF manufacturing process. This section details the algorithm used to recreate the FFF manufacturing process, structural analysis of the digital recreation and optimization of the FFF process parameters.

A schematic of the data flow is described in figure 2. The python core module was developed by the authors of this paper. The python core module communicates with a slicer (Slic3r), a meshing tool (HyperMesh), a FE solver (Abaqus) and an optimization tool (HyperStudy).

Figure 2: Simulation method

Slic3r is a geometry slicing tool that slices the input geometry in Z and generates a path on each layer which the extruder follows. The slicing operation is governed by FFF parameters which are communicated to slic3r in an INI format. Slic3r is operated in batch mode to output a GCode.

The GCode parser generates a series of images – one for each layer (figure 3(a)) by analysing the GCode and interpreting the extruder movements and the amount of material extruded. The generated images are passed to a contour recognition algorithm to recognize the material fill pattern in each layer (figure 3(b)). The recognized contour lines will be in pixel coordinates of the recognized image and have to be mapped back to the coordinate system of the input geometry.

The STL analyser module recognizes salient dimensions of the input geometry needed to map the contour lines from the pixel coordinate system to the coordinate system of the input geometry.

Hypermesh uses the mapped contour lines to generate 2D surface of the fill pattern in each layer. The 2D surface is meshed with the QI optimize mesh algorithm. The generated mesh is exported to the mesh analysis module.

The mesh analysis module recognizes features of the mesh that are essential to build the FE model. Boundary nodes are identified to apply loads and boundary conditions. Material orientations for each element is assigned with respect to the extruder movement vector along the element. Material orientations are important because when chopped fibres are extruded, they tend to show preferential alignment along the direction of movement of the extruder. The mesh analysis module also extrudes the 2D shell mesh into a 3D solid mesh. The element facets at the top and bottom (along the Z direction) of the solid mesh are identified to impose contact conditions at the interfaces between layers.

The Abaqus interface module builds the FE model to perform a static structural analysis on the mesh generated by HyperMesh. The Abaqus interface module also uses the boundary nodes and element facets identified by the mesh analysis module to impose appropriate contact constraints, loads and boundary conditions. The material orientation vector for each element is translated to a format useable by Abaqus. The Abaqus interface also parses through the output generated by Abaqus and calculates the stiffness and maximum stress based failure indices of the analysed structure.

Hyperstudy uses the stiffness and failure indices calculated by the Abaqus interface module to constrain the optimization routine with an objective to minimize the weight of the manufactured part.

Figure 3: a) Image of the surface generated by parsing a GCode. (b) Results from the image recognition algorithm (Green lines represent the recognized contours and colours are inverted because of a requirement of the contour recognition algorithm)

2.1 Static structural analysis

A static structural analysis was carried out to determine the effect of the process parameters on the stiffness of the manufactured part. The analysis follows guidelines specified in ISO standard 527. The test bar considered is of type 1A (fig. 4). A fixed constraint is imposed on one end of the test bar and a negative pressure load imposed on the other end. Relative displacements of nodes which are gauge length apart (prescribed in ISO standard 527) were used to calculate the strain. The cross section area of the test section (in between dotted lines in fig 4) is twice the cross section area of the padding (region outside the dotted lines in fig 4 where the load and boundary conditions are applied). The stress experienced by the test section will be twice the applied pressure. There might exist stress concentrations around the curved regions and in the vicinity of the applied load but, the stress will be uniform in the test section.

Figure 4: Schematic of the simulated test specimen

2.1.1 Approximation

The contact constraint used in the model to various layers across interfaces assumes infinite stiffness and infinite strength. A strength based contact condition can be imposed at layer-layer interfaces (weld lines) only after analysing the effects of temperature on polymer bonding at the weld lines. Such an analysis is outside the scope of this paper.

2.2 Optimization

The objective of the optimization was weight reduction with strength constraint imposed on the optimization. The optimization demonstrated in the paper uses a genetic algorithm. A random based algorithm was required because the random change of structural responses when the parameter infill type is varied. The design variables chosen for the optimization demonstrator are listed in table 1. The number of design variables and range of allowed values were restricted due to computational considerations.

PARAMETER	VALUES
INFILL PATTERN	Rectilinear, Cubic, Honeycomb
INFILL DENSITY	0% - 90% (100% in case of rectilinear)
TOP AND BOTTOM SOLID LAYERS	0 - 3
PERIMETERS	1 - 3

Table 1: List of design variables and range of allowed values.

3 Results and Discussion

The method developed in this paper was verified experimentally by manufacturing samples made of three different materials. ColorFabb XT, ColorFabb XT CF 20 and Proto Pasta HTPLA CF were the 3 materials used. ‘CF’ in the name of the material indicates the material contains chopped carbon fibre. All 3 materials were tested using ISO 527 tensile standards to measure the elastic modulus, failure stress, failure strain, yield stress and peak stress. Results from ISO 527 standard tests are given in table 2.

PROPERTY	COLORFABB XT	COLORFABB XT CF20	PROTO PASTA HTPLA CF	TESTING STANDARD
ELASTIC MODULUS (MPa)	2208	8175	7190	ISO 527
FAILURE STRESS (MPa)	28.45	58.162	72.48	ISO 527
FAILURE STRAIN (1)	0.58582	0.08421	0.03190	ISO 527
YIELD STRESS (MPa)	51.54	74.79	78.023	ISO 527
PEAK STRESS (MPa)	51.5	74.7	78.038	ISO 527

Table 2: Tensile properties

Adding carbon fibre to ColorFabb XT increases the peak stress by a factor of 1.45 but, the material becomes very brittle - failure strain becomes one seventh of the virgin polymer.

Proto Pasta HTPLA CF is the only material among all 3 of the considered materials which exhibits crystallinity and is the most brittle with a failure strain of 0.03 [6].

3.1 Knockdown in mechanical properties

An additively manufactured component will be non-monolithic. Weld lines among other artefacts of additive manufacturing will conspire to knockdown the mechanical performance of the component. The knockdown factor (η_k) relates the mechanical performance of an injection moulded sample to that of an additively manufactured sample (eq. 1). A model to calculate the knockdown factor does not exist and developing such a model is outside the scope of this paper.

The knockdown factor will potentially be a function of the power of the extruder (stepper) motor, temperature history etc. To overcome the complexity of developing a model for knockdown factor, it was assumed that the non FFF machine related parameters except infill angle does not affect the knockdown factor. All test samples were made with the same machine and at infill angles of $+45^\circ$, -45° alternating between successive layers. Table 3 compares the weight and elastic modulus of injection moulded and additively manufactured (rectilinear 100% infill) tensile test bars.

$$\eta_k = \frac{\text{Property}_{AM}}{\text{Property}_{Injection\ molded}} \quad (1)$$

Materials with carbon fibre experiences a higher degree of knockdown for stiffness. A potential source of reduction in stiffness can be due to the preferential alignment of fibres. Figure 5 shows microscope images of ColorFabb XT CF20 injection moulded (fig. 5(b)) and additively manufactured (fig. 5(a)). The fibres in the injection moulded sample seem to be randomly oriented whereas fibres in the additively manufactured sample seem to show preferential orientation. Further experimental studies are needed to confirm the preferential orientation hypothesis.

	<i>COLORFABB XT</i>		<i>COLORFABB XT CF20</i>		<i>PROTO PASTA HTPLA CF</i>	
	Stiffness (MPa)	Weight (g)	Stiffness (MPa)	Weight (g)	Stiffness (MPa)	Weight (g)
INJECTION MOULDED	2208	13.29	8175	14.06	7190	13.13
AM	2030	11.5	3681	11.19	4990	10.9
η_k	0.92	0.86	0.45	0.80	0.69	0.83

Table 3: Knockdown in properties because of additive manufacturing

Figure 5: (a) Micrograph of an additively manufactured part (Colorfabb XT CF20) (b) Micrograph of an injection molded part (Colorfabb XT CF20)

3.2 Stiffness variation due to FFF parameters

Three infill types are considered - Cubic, Rectilinear and Honeycomb at 20%, 50% and 80% (and 100% for rectilinear) densities. ISO standard test bars were manufactured with ColorFabb XT, ColorFabb XT CF20, and Proto Pasta HTPLA CF. The test bars were tested in tension. The experimental results were compared with results from simulation and are presented in this section. Knockdown factors (η_k) for stiffness from table 5 were used in the simulation.

ColorFabb XT

Graphs in figure 6 (a, b, c) compare the simulated and experimental stiffness of a tensile test specimen manufactured with ColorFabb XT. The maximum deviation of simulated stiffness from experimental values is 11.5% for cubic infill at 80% infill density and the minimum deviation is 0.12% for 50% honeycomb infill.

ColorFabb XT CF20

Graphs in figure 6 (d, e, f) compare the simulated and experimental stiffness of a tensile test specimen manufactured with ColorFabb XT CF20. Experimental stiffness for honeycomb infill (fig. 6(e)) at 80% density is higher than the experimental stiffness for rectilinear 100% infill. The author does not have a hypothesis to describe this anomaly. Further experimentation comparing stiffness of different batches of additively manufactured samples will shed more light on the cause of this anomaly. The deviation between the simulated and experimental values for ColorFabb XT CF20 is similar to the deviation for ColorFabb XT with a maximum deviation of 14.38% for cubic infill at 80% infill density and the minimum deviation is 0.15% for 50% honeycomb infill.

Figure 6: Variation stiffness with infill density for specimens manufactured with Colorfabb XT - (a) Honeycomb infill (b) Rectilinear infill (c) Cubic infill

Proto Pasta HTPLA CF

Graphs in figure 7 compare the simulated and experimental stiffness of a tensile test specimen manufactured with Proto Pasta HTPLA CF. The trend of deviation between the simulated and experimental stiffness for Proto Pasta HTPLA CF is very similar to the deviation for the other materials. Simulations for honeycomb infill matches closely with experimental results. For rectilinear infill, the simulated and experimental stiffness follows a similar trend but, has a higher degree of deviation compared to the stiffness for honeycomb infill. The maximum deviation of simulated stiffness from experimental values is 16.07% for cubic infill at 80% infill density and the minimum deviation is 1.23% for 50% honeycomb infill.

Figure 7: Variation stiffness with infill density for specimens manufactured with Proto Pasta HTPLA CF - (a) Honeycomb infill (b) Rectilinear infill (c) Cubic infill

3.2.1 Deviation from experimental values

Studying batch to batch variability and machine variability of stiffness could make the experimental results statistically more accurate and potentially shed light on a few of the anomalies observed. Machine variability studies are important because industries can have high precision printers which can print better quality samples than the machine used in this paper. The huge number of samples that are required pushes the variability studies outside the scope of this paper.

In the simulation environment, tie constraints are used to bind the various layers together. A tie constraint, by definition is infinitely stiff. The infinite stiffness can induce artificial stress concentrations in the vicinity of the constraint which will have an effect on the stiffness of the numerical model. Cohesive bonding is a candidate to replace tie constraint. Stiffness laws can be defined for cohesive bonds which makes it possible to study inter layer damage initiation and propagation. Relative complexity in enforcing a cohesive bond makes its implementation computationally expensive. Exploring various contact models could be studied in a continuation project of this paper.

3.3 Optimization

An optimization was carried out using a genetic algorithm with a population size of 10 on a simple cuboid of dimensions 10mm x 10mm x 2mm. The bounds of design variables are given in table 1. An extrusion width of 0.45 and a layer height of 0.2 mm was used. The demonstrated optimization is a proof of concept that the model obtained from the developed platform is suitable for optimization.

The cuboid is subjected to a uniformly distributed tensile load with a magnitude of 1000Pa on a surface with dimensions 10mm x 2mm. A fixed constraint is imposed on nodes on the surface opposite of the surface on which load is applied. The average displacement of nodes on the surface with the applied load is used to constrain the optimization algorithm. A maximum average displacement constraint (4.5E-5mm) is imposed on the optimization with the objective to minimize weight. The weight of the part for a given set of design variables can be calculated from the length of filament used. Slic3r - The slicing tool used, outputs the length of filament used when generating the GCode.

A contour of nodal displacement along the direction of the applied load on a layer of the studied cuboid is given in fig. 8. The cuboid is filled with cubic infill pattern at a density of 50% in fig. 8.

The generation index vs average nodal displacement and generation index vs length of filament used plots in fig. 9 shows the progress of the objective and constraint over generations. For the dimensions of the cuboid and parameters of the normal distribution curve, optima was reached in generation 2 but, the optimization algorithm stopped only after stopping criteria was satisfied in generation 11. Graphs in fig. 10 shows the variation of the objective function and constraint over various iterations - 10 iterations per generation (population size). The optimal values for the design variables are given in table 4. The minimum possible filament usage for the constraint specified is $80.33mm$ which translates to $0.2501g$. The average displacement of nodes on the loaded surface at optimal values of the design variables is $4.42E-5mm$ (constraint: $4.5E-5mm$).

Local variations in nodal displacement because of the shape of the infill (fig. 8) could be a potential reason for the optimization algorithm not finding a solution for which the average nodal displacement equals the constraint. Another possible explanation could be the low population size. Minima given by statistical techniques like genetic algorithm cannot be guaranteed to be the absolute minima of the objective function (subject to constraints). Gradient based optimization algorithms might be more efficient in finding the minima but, the erratic behaviour of the *infill type* parameter restricts the use of a single gradient based optimization run. Several gradient based optimization runs (one for every infill type) could prove to be more efficient compared to statistical techniques.

Figure 8: Nodal displacement contours in a layer of the cuboid with cubic infill

Figure 9: Evolution of the objective function and constraint over generations

Figure 10: Variation of the objective function and constraint for all function evaluations

PARAMETER	OPTIMAL VALUE
INFILL TYPE	Cubic
INFILL DENSITY	85.7%
PERIMETERS	3
TOP AND BOTTOM SOLID LAYERS	1

Table 4: Optimal values for the design variables

4 Conclusion

Modern additive manufacturing has been around only for a few decades and a substantial amount of innovation and development has been happening in recent years to increase industrial adoption of AM. The optimization platform developed in this paper will help reduce the trials needed to successfully manufacture a part, thus increasing the adoption of FFF in the industry.

The optimization routine developed in this paper is one of the very few platforms developed for FFF. Key steps and challenges in optimizing FFF process parameters were identified. An optimization platform integrating all required steps was developed.

The approach developed in this paper can also be used to simulate the temperature variation during the FFF manufacturing process. The temperature history of the manufacturing process is required to calculate the degree of bonding at the interfaces (weld lines). The sequential deposition of molten material will result in a temperature gradient. The difference in temperature across the part that is being manufactured can cause warping. The procedure to implement a thermal model is described in the first author's thesis titled "Additive manufacturing: Optimization of process parameters for fused filament fabrication" [6]

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